

Annual Report for May 1, 2023-April 30, 2024

RCD Nexus

NSF CI CoE: Demo Pilot: Advancing Research Computing and Data: Strategic Tools, Practices, and Professional Development

[NSF Grant OAC-2100003](#)

May 1, 2023-April 30, 2024

For Public Distribution

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About the RCD Nexus

The RCD Nexus is funded by NSF's Office of Advanced Cyberinfrastructure as an NSF Cyberinfrastructure Center of Excellence (CI CoE) demo pilot. It is a Research Computing and Data (RCD) Resource and Career Center that creates tools, practices, and professional development resources to support individuals and institutions. RCD Nexus both leverages and augments the infrastructure of the Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC) in order to reach, support, and engage with Research Computing and Data and other related professionals. CaRCC is uniquely positioned to support and grow the RCD community, with a vision to advance the frontiers of research by improving the effectiveness of RCD professionals and organizations. The CaRCC community is growing rapidly, with People Network membership increasing by more than 150% per year. Activities are expanding, including multiple new working- and interest- groups, as well as increasing partnerships with other RCD partners.

CaRCC's People Network and groups help RCD Nexus reach its intended audience, and the RCD Nexus has, in turn, helped the People Network and CaRCC expand rapidly, both in numbers and scope. With CaRCC's rapid growth, it has become increasingly difficult for it to be managed and overseen by volunteers alone. RCD Nexus has thus filled a critical role by providing central staff and resources to ensure organization, consistency, and professionalism as CaRCC progresses toward becoming a more formal professional society. RCD Nexus-funded staff are largely leading the general administration, management, communications, and engagement efforts – which allows CaRCC volunteers and members to focus on sharing their RCD-related knowledge.

The main areas of emphasis for the RCD Nexus include:

- A more robust and sustainable implementation of the RCD Capabilities Model and a new Community Dataset portal
- Conducting an RCD Professional Staffing Survey and sharing the results
- Advancing the adoption of the Human Resources (HR) Job Family Framework
- Developing a Career Arcs resource for RCD professionals
- Curating leading practices for staff professional development, and for involving students in RCD workforce development

For information about the RCD Nexus, please visit the project website: <http://rcd-nexus.org>.

About This Report

This report represents the project year of NSF grant OAC-210003 from May 1, 2023 to April 30, 2024.

Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the National Science Foundation.

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For updates to this report and other reports from the RCD Nexus, please visit <http://rcd-nexus.org>.

Executive Summary

The RCD Nexus project continues to both leverage and augment the Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC) in order to reach, support, and engage with Research Computing and Data (RCD) professionals. These central services and support remain essential to CaRCC's success during this period of continued organizational growth. RCD Nexus currently fills this role by providing central staff, leadership, and resources as CaRCC works towards a long-term sustainability plan. Highlights for the reporting period fall into the following categories:

Communications and Engagement – We held a talk by Katy Antypas from the National Science Foundation (NSF) about the National Artificial Intelligence Research Resource (NAIRR) pilot project that was attended by 300 people, with the recording viewed by more than 150 people. We also completed several successful events, including the third RCD Nexus Day, which was attended by 95 people and provided travel support for 33. We launched a “Monthly Welcome” series to greet new community members. We developed a privacy policy for our new constituent relationship management (CRM) system and began using it.

Developing Career Arcs – We continued our work to investigate the factors that influence RCD professionals in the course of their careers, conducting 14 in-depth interviews with a range of RCD professionals, and began the process of coding these to identify distinctive themes, factors, and influences. We have developed a model for how we plan to visualize the common paths to help RCD professionals in their own career planning, and to help hiring managers better understand where recruitment efforts can be effective.

RCD Capabilities Model – We completed the 2.0 version of our more robust and sustainable implementation of the RCD Capabilities Model and successfully transitioned to the new tool. We released several feature upgrades, and incorporated the latest institutional metadata from IPEDS, Carnegie, and the Department of Education. We launched the initial version of the data visualization portal allowing institutions to explore community data and benchmark their Capabilities Assessment results relative to the community. The Focused Tools committee released a Capabilities Model Engagement Guide and Script to support institutions in early development of RCD services and support. We contributed the EPSCoR CI Workshop project report,¹ “Minding the Gap: Leveraging Cyberinfrastructure to Transform EPSCoR Jurisdictions”² and continued consulting with the American Indian Higher Education Consortium (AIHEC) in support of their Cyberinfrastructure Strategic Planning (CISP) Initiative.

¹ NSF (OIA) Award 2033483, Award 2033519, and Award 2033514, Collaborative Research: “Building Research Cyberinfrastructure in EPSCoR Jurisdictions: Assessment, Planning and Partnerships”

² Bayrd, V., Jacobs, G., Schmitz, P., Strachan, S., Clemins, P., & Harris, F. C. J. (2023). Minding the Gap: Leveraging Cyberinfrastructure to Transform EPSCoR Jurisdictions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8097562>

RCD Staff Resources – The Staff Workforce Development workstream held a workshop attended by nearly 50 people with the topic of “Onboarding: Introducing the Who, What, Where, When, and Why to new RCD Staff” as part of the RCD Nexus Day at PEARC23. The materials generated from this workshop were further refined, resulting in a paper describing a framework for an RCD onboarding process titled “Onboarding Research Computing and Data Professionals,” submitted as a short paper to PEARC24 and the publication of an RCD onboarding checklist.

Student Workforce Development – The RCD Student Workforce group has grown significantly during the reporting period to a total of 78 members who meet at least bi-monthly. Onboarding remains a significant focus of both our discussions and in the development of related tools and products. We hosted several presentations during the period, including a well-received panel of former RCD students who shared the impact of their experiences as student employees in RCD.

Job Family Matrix Adoption – Interest in the HR Job Family Matrix remains high. To date there have been 366 total downloads from 299 unique emails across 174 different institutions, including 66 downloads from the past year.

RCD Workforce Survey – During the reporting period, we began planning a new survey, but first conducted an analysis of the 2021 survey data questions and focused on understanding the relationship between activities and roles and how they change through the lens from researcher-facing to systems-facing, software-facing, or data-facing. This resulted in a PEARC’24 short paper submission. Key findings confirmed quantitatively what many of us have experienced anecdotally. For example, a large number of life sciences professionals become facilitators, whereas computer and information or physical science professionals have a broad distribution of types of roles they play in research computing.

Program Administration – In addition to the project and budget management tasks associated with the grant, we coordinated the June 2023 CaRCC Annual meeting and produced a [related report](#). We planned and executed the second annual RCD Nexus Day co-located with PEARC23, which also [yielded a report](#). We led CaRCC Chairs Monthly meetings and the Logistics and Engagement Operations groups meetings. We also started a new effort to explore potential membership and financial models to support long term CaRCC sustainability.

Looking Forward – RCD Nexus support has provided critical infrastructure and central support for the growing CaRCC organization and serves to amplify the impact of CaRCC volunteers. However, the current level of support falls short of overall needs, hampering progress on important priorities. Looking forward, in addition to a number of specific priorities related to refining and developing additional tools for the RCD community, we must dedicate significant effort towards developing a long-term financial model to ensure CaRCC’s sustainability.

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1 Communications and Engagement

Accomplishments for the reporting period in the areas of communications and engagement include:

- Hosting and promoting an invited talk by Katy Antypas from the National Science Foundation about the National Artificial Intelligence Research Resource (NAIRR) pilot project. The presentation was viewed live by 300 people, with [the recording](#) viewed by more than 150 people. (Completed March 2024)
- Maintaining an active LinkedIn and Facebook presence to communicate with a broader audience about RCD Nexus and CaRCC tools and activities (Ongoing.)
- Developing a privacy policy for our cloud-based Constituent Relationship Management (CRM) software tool and beginning use of the tool for CaRCC list management. (Completed February 2024)
- Completing communications and outreach efforts at several events including PEARC23, and Supercomputing 23.
- Developing new print materials and event signage (Ongoing)
- Designing a new website template for CaRCC and RCD Nexus. (Set to launch May 2024)

Engagement efforts and events

During the reporting period, the CaRCC Engagement working group, under co-leadership of RCD Nexus lead, Claire Mizumoto completed work on several efforts. The group enables the continued rapid growth of the People Network through leadership, membership drives, and identifying opportunities for in-person outreach through events.

Some specific efforts during the period include:

- Rolled out new “Monthly Welcome” series to greet new members of the People Network, answer their questions, and ensure they know about and get integrated into CaRCC groups and activities relevant to their specific needs and interests.
- Held CaRCC Parade Event in January 2023, providing an update for the existing CaRCC community and providing information on CaRCC groups and activities for new members.
- Completed the second annual “Bring Your Colleague to CaRCC” recruitment effort in January 2024 that encouraged existing members to invite their colleagues to join the People Network and/or attend working or interest group calls.
- Hosted CaRCC/RCD Nexus booth (in partnership with Internet2) at the PEARC23 Conference to inform attendees about CaRCC and RCD Nexus resources.
- Held a well-attended “Coffee with CaRCC” event at the Supercomputing Conference. Current members of CaRCC and those interested in getting involved with CaRCC met for a casual networking and informational event at the Internet2 booth.

Blog posts - RCD Nexus produced the following blog posts, in addition to the monthly posts announcing all the People Network and related sessions.

- April 9, 2024: [New Release: RCD Nexus Capabilities Model Visualization Portal](#)
- April 3, 2024: [Watch the video: The National Artificial Intelligence Research Resource \(NAIRR\) by Katie Antypas](#)
- March 18, 2024: [CaRCC Special Presentation: The National Artificial Intelligence Research Resource \(NAIRR\) by Katie Antypas](#)
- March 17, 2024 [New! CaRCC Monthly Welcome Events](#)
- January 30, 2024 [Capabilities Model Assessment Tool Upgraded to Version 2.1](#)
- December 20, 2023 [2024 CaRCC Parade & Bring Your Colleagues to CaRCC!](#)
- November 27, 2023 [Read the report: RCD Nexus Day 2023](#)
- November 9, 2023 [Minding the Gap: EPSCoR CI Workshop report released](#)
- November 2, 2023 [New Capabilities Model Assessment Tool Now Available](#)
- October 16, 2023 [Seeking beta-testers for the new RCD Capabilities Model Tool](#)
- September 14, 2023 [Where does RCD sit in the organization?](#)
- September 14, 2023 [Q&A about CaRCC's new membership management tool](#)
- August 28, 2023 [Read the report: 2023 CaRCC Annual Strategy and Planning Retreat](#)
- August 23, 2023 [CaRCC Volunteer Opportunities](#)
- July 21, 2023 [CaRCC activities at PEARC23](#)
- July 20, 2023 [Revised CaRCC Overview](#)
- May 2, 2023 [RCD Nexus Day at PEARC23](#)

RCD professional events

RCD Nexus held several successful events during the reporting period, bringing the community together to network and discuss common issues and challenges. CaRCC/RCD Nexus events help to forge professional relationships within the RCD community, and also serve to share and improve the products and tools produced by the RCD Nexus project.

2023 CaRCC Annual Retreat – This meeting brings together CaRCC chairs of working, interest, and operations groups as well as the People Network co-chairs and track coordinators, the CaRCC and RCD Nexus Advisory committees, and others from the broader community, including leaders from organizations such as Campus Champions, EDUCAUSE, and US-RSE, to review activities, determine future activities, and set strategic priorities. The 2023 meeting was held over three days in May in Rosemont(Chicago), IL. The meeting [yielded a report](#) with several action items.

2023 RCD Nexus Day – RCD Nexus Day 2023 brought together 95 research computing and data (RCD) professionals from institutions across the U.S. The event took place on July 23, 2023, and was an official co-located event of the PEARC'23 conference in Portland, Oregon. Thirty-three attendees received travel support, which allowed them to attend both RCD Nexus Day and the

full PEARC23 conference. In addition to a combined opening session and an evening networking session, the event included two concurrent workshops. Workshop 1 was related to using the RCD Capabilities Model assessment tools and was led by Patrick Schmitz, while Workshop 2 was on the topic of staff and student onboarding and led by Claire Mizumoto. The [2023 RCD Nexus Day Final Report](#) provides details and recommendations identified at the workshops.

CaRCC Town Hall at PEARC23 – This standing-room-only event brought together more than 150 members of the broader CaRCC/RCD community to learn about current CaRCC projects and initiatives, followed by an open discussion during which community members provided feedback and shared ideas to inform future CaRCC activities.

PEARC23 Best Full Paper in the workforce track - Several members of CaRCC and Campus Champions Leadership teams collaborated on a stakeholder mapping survey with Joel Gershenfeld to produce “Professionalization of Research Computing and Data: An Expanded Agenda [Cutcher-Gershenfeld, 2023] which won best paper in the workforce track at PEARC23.

New working and interest groups

During the reporting period, a new HIPAA Challenges working group was formed. This group started as a discussion about the challenge of supporting researchers working with HIPAA data. Through these discussions, the group realized there was a substantial story to tell about how HIPAA impacts research negatively and what could be done to mitigate it. The group is now working to turn the content into a white paper, share it with the community to get input and endorsement, then present it to policy makers.

Communications and Outreach interest group

Formed in April 2024, this new group will discuss topics such as:

- How to communicate technical or complex topics clearly and concisely
- How best to explain the concept of RCD
- How to reach and communicate with different audiences
- The value and pitfalls of various communication outlets

The group will also allow those who communicate about research IT and RCD to get to know each other and help amplify each other's messages, where appropriate.

2 Developing Career Arcs

RCD Nexus is developing a model of Career Arcs for RCD Professionals to explain career options and help existing RCD professionals pursue professional development and advancement.

Our key objectives are to address the following set of challenges, as identified in a series of workshops and meetings:

- Managers need better resources and the ability to offer defined career paths, so their staff are not forced to seek growth opportunities outside the RCD profession.
- Many RCD professionals say they see no clear path for career advancement; this is especially so for data-centric and researcher-facing roles.
- There is a national shortage of RCD (CI) personnel and high employee turnover, with significant training needed to orient new employees.
- There is no formal talent pipeline seeking to join the RCD field. Students who are studying in relevant programs do not have an easy way to learn about or enter the field.
- RCD personnel experience precarious employment with few opportunities for advancement.

We continued work to develop a framework for describing the roles and career arcs of RCD professionals and distributed content through community engagement. Specific activities included:

- Recruiting for and conducting a series of in-depth interviews of RCD professionals to better understand their choices, motivations, and the factors that enable success.
- Coding interview transcripts and synthesizing results into personas and common factors that represent typical experiences across the community. Each will be enriched with anonymized quotes, to make them personal without identifying real individuals.

We have researched options and approaches to the development of a visualization of career arcs and pathways. Once the interviews and associated analyses are complete, we will draft one or two visualizations and then either hold a workshop or a series of community outreach sessions to get feedback on the materials we develop. We will then produce a companion paper to the visualization with recommended practices for hiring managers for both recruitment as well as retention of RCD professional staff. Much of this activity will be conducted in collaboration with the Staff and Student Workforce Development workstreams.

Working group members also contributed to the ACM PEARC23 paper “Career Phases in Research Computing and Data”³

³ Middelkoop, T., Mizumoto, C., Strachan, S., Balamurugan, D., Delinger, S., Fosso Tande, J., McCaffrey, D., Myatt James, A., Reddy, D., & Schmitz, P. (2023, September 10). Career Phases in Research Computing and Data. ACM PEARC '23: Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC23), Portland OR, USA. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3569951.3597562>

3 RCD Capabilities Model

The goal of the RCD Capabilities Model (RCD CM) workstream is to develop a more robust and sustainable implementation of the RCD Capabilities Model assessment tool and an associated data-exploration portal that eliminates the need to create a host of individual reports by hand.

We originally had two broad objectives for the RCD CM workstream:

- Implement a 2.0 version of the RCD Capabilities Model assessment tool and data exploration portal
- Expand consulting and support services to ensure a broad range of institutions can use the model and incorporate it into strategic planning work for their respective RCD programs

We originally intended to implement the 2.0 version of the assessment tool on an existing platform, but we found candidate platforms lacked necessary functionality. We considered continued use of the prototype implementation (augmented with improved help support), but during design and implementation for the data portal, an approach emerged to build a web application that would provide a superior user experience and better integration of assessment data with the new portal without excessive development cost. We resolved to follow this approach and our resulting product confirms this was a good choice.

We heard from a number of smaller or under-resourced institutions and emerging RCD programs that they found the existing RCD Capabilities Model to be overwhelming, and/or that they lack the resources to complete that level of assessment. In response to this community feedback, the RCD Capabilities Model working group at CaRCC added an additional objective to better meet the needs of these smaller institutions and emerging RCD programs by developing a set of focused tools that helps them identify necessary elements to bootstrap an RCD support program (this activity is described below).

During the development phase for the new portal, we continued our support for the prototype implementation of the RCD Capabilities Model assessment tool and the annual community datasets derived from contributed assessments. We converted all the data contributed by Institutions using the initial implementation and imported this data into the new system, ensuring that the community dataset would reflect the full history of the tool going back to 2019.

When we released the new implementation of the assessment tool, many institutions engaged and we received strong positive feedback. To date, a total of 207 institutions have requested copies of the RCD Capabilities Model assessment tool for evaluation (either through the old request mechanism or as RCD profiles on the new web-based tool), representing all 50 US

States, two territories and the District of Columbia, five Canadian provinces, and several other countries outside North America. Since our launch about three years ago, 60 institutions have completed and contributed 87 assessments (some choose to repeat the assessment to assess progress over time), representing 35 US States and one US Territory (including 13 EPSCoR jurisdictions), and two Canadian Provinces.

We also released the new Data Visualization Portal (<https://portal.rcd-nexus.org/dataviz/>) that provides public access to much of the CaRCC Capabilities Model Community Dataset. Users can explore various facets of the dataset including:

- Demographics of the community of users (those who have a profile and are working on an assessment) and contributors (those who completed an assessment), including map-based views as well as charts.
- Capabilities Data including both high-level summary charts as well as topic-level charts.
- Various filters to explore subsets of the community, and select different graph view options to compare the average capabilities coverage of different communities (e.g., Public vs. Private institutions, EPSCoR vs. Non-EPSCoR, etc.).
- A benchmarking view for any of the Capabilities Data views for users to compare their coverage to a filtered set of other institutions.

Additional functionality has been requested by community members as they use the new tools, and we are addressing it in subsequent feature releases. This includes:

- Chart your own Journey (discussed below under “Focused Tools work”)
- Ability to copy parts of a previous assessment into a current one (for areas that are largely unchanged).
- Support to re-order marked priorities with a simple drag-and-drop user interface.
- More visualization options including summary priorities data, new graph types for capabilities data (e.g., “violin” graphs).
- Support to select a given set of contributors for benchmarking.
- Additional Help Docs and introductory material for new users.

Other work:

- We continued our support of the EPSCoR CI Workshop project⁴ with data and analysis included in that project’s final report “Minding the Gap: Leveraging Cyberinfrastructure to Transform EPSCoR Jurisdictions” [Bayrd, 2023].

⁴ NSF (OIA) Award 2033483, Award 2033519, and Award 2033514, Collaborative Research: “Building Research Cyberinfrastructure in EPSCoR Jurisdictions: Assessment, Planning and Partnerships”

Focused Tools work

The Focused Tools Committee was established within the Capabilities Model working group to address the RCD support needs of smaller and/or under-resourced institutions and emerging RCD programs. The committee held a series of focus groups and workshops to get more input from the community about how to help smaller schools and emerging research programs develop their institutional research support. Feedback from the community pointed to two things that are needed:

1. It is essential to start with a conversation about research support and align on terminology and goals.
2. We must provide a more focused version of the Capabilities Model assessment tool to better meet the needs of these smaller institutions and emerging RCD programs.

The Focused Tools Committee has produced a guide to help start a conversation about research support and align on terminology and goals [Hicks and Ghahramani, 2024]. The guide is just the starting point but offers suggestions on how to start a dialog about where an institution is on their research support journey. Together with the full assessment and data portal, tools such as these will constitute a suite of coordinated tools that respond to the needs of RCD programs from inception through maturity.

The work of the Focused Tools Committee has informed the design of several new features planned for an upcoming release of the Capabilities Model assessment tool, known informally as the “Chart your own Journey” functionality. These features will allow users to select (i.e., to *focus on*) a subset of the topics within the five Facings, and complete only those topics. The resulting data will still be incorporated into the community dataset, and can be benchmarked against peers.

Engagement with American Indian Higher Education Consortium

We continue to use a small amount of our consulting resources in an engagement with the American Indian Higher Education Consortium (AIHEC, <http://www.aihec.org/>) in support of their Cyberinfrastructure Strategic Planning (CISP) Initiative. The AIHEC Cyberinfrastructure (CI) Team advances the science, technology, engineering and math (STEM) and education programs at the nation’s 37 Tribal College and Universities (TCUs) by implementing a comprehensive CI capacity-building strategy focusing on the colleges’ STEM faculty and CI support staff. With support from external partners and regional institutions, this comprehensive CI strategy focuses on CI training, planning, and community-building involving both STEM faculty and TCU IT organizations, providing the resources, technical assistance and national network to advance participating TCUs toward CI-readiness and CI-enabled STEM research and education programs.

We are engaged on the AIHEC Cyberinfrastructure Strategic Planning (CISP) Initiative, “Developing a technology roadmap at the TCUs to support their academic, research, business, and public service missions.”

During this period we:

- Contributed to assessments at several TCUs, including regular meetings with TCU IT leadership, supporting the completion of their assessments, analysis of the resulting data, and initial work towards recommendations that will inform an IT strategic plan.
- Met with the AIHEC/CISP consultant team to share experiences and give them visibility into related efforts in the RCD community.

Outreach and communications

We provide periodic reports and posts with analysis of the community dataset, although with the release of the data portal, we no longer need to publish the extensive annual data reports. We facilitate workshops and make presentations at ACM PEARC and other conferences (e.g., the Mississippi HPC Conference), and conduct focus groups, etc. for working group activities.

Office hours

As part of support for the RCD CM we have established regular office hours to provide support for institutions completing the Capabilities Model and for individuals needing more specific help. Discussions among individuals from participating institutions proved to be supportive and beneficial to both institutions and to the RCD CM Working Group with everything from approaches to campus participation to complete the survey, clarification on specific questions, and improvements for future versions of the Capabilities Model.

Office hours have been held monthly throughout the reporting period. Additional email follow-up addressed directly to working group members and to the capsmode-discuss@carcc.org mailing list have also resulted from office hours discussions.

Members of the RCD CM working group have also met individually with representatives from institutions requesting specific attention to their questions about the Model and the submission process, as well as a discussion about strategies for engagement and best practices to complete the Model.

The RCD CM Working Group will continue to host regular office hours, generally staffed by two to four working group members at each session. They will continue to be provided remotely via Zoom and regularly advertised to the RCD CM participating institutions, general RCD community mailing lists, and the CaRCC and RCD Nexus websites and in relevant blog posts and newsletters.

4 RCD Staff Resources

RCD Nexus community development effort continues in the area of staff resources to support RCD professionals and institutions with RCD practitioners who support research activities. The key objectives are to address the challenges identified in a series of discussions, call for position papers and program experiences documentation, and a workshop.

These include:

- Identifying leading practices and common elements among staff workforce development programs.
- Propagating various models to support workforce development for staff RCD practitioners (as well as undergraduate and graduate students in collaboration with the RCD Nexus Student Workforce workstream effort.)
- Employing a “train the trainers” model to build a community of trainers that, in turn, helps educate other RCD professionals on workforce development topics.

The materials gathered will provide the basis for an analysis to identify gaps and needs for additional training programs that would facilitate the transition from other positions into RCD roles, and, for example, developing existing RCD staff into RCD leadership roles. We have found, in order to accomplish this, we first must foster the RCD community to understand these efforts. Unlike some of the other work within the RCD Nexus, this effort is addressing newly identified needs, rather than continuing and growing efforts already underway.

Building a workforce development community

During the reporting period, we continued to grow a community of interested RCD professionals and provide opportunities for individuals to self-identify as participants in these workforce development efforts. In addition, we are seeing engagement by supervisors, managers, and directors who are shaping the RCD programs at institutions around the country and beyond.

RCD Nexus Day: In July 2023, at the RCD Nexus Day co-located with PEARC23, the Staff Workforce Development workstream held an all-day workshop with the topic of “Onboarding: Introducing the Who, What, Where, When, and Why to new RCD Staff” with nearly 50 people in attendance. The goal was not only to be informative and spark discussion, but also to work towards deliverables that would be useful in the broader RCD community. The materials generated from the workshop were further refined and developed by the CaRCC Staff and Student Workforce Development Interest Group resulting in a paper describing a framework for an RCD onboarding process titled “Onboarding Research Computing and Data Professionals,” submitted as a short paper to PEARC24 and the publication of an RCD onboarding checklist

titled the “An Onboarding Checklist for Research Computing and Data Professionals.” Additional details about the workshop can be found in the full RCD Nexus Day 2023 report:

- Gladys Andino, Scott L. Delinger, Jacob Fosso Tande, Timothy Middelkoop, Claire Mizumoto, David P. Reddy, and Michael D. Weiner. "An Onboarding Checklist for Research Computing and Data Professionals," Zenodo, 2024.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11074226>
- Schmitz, Patrick, Claire Mizumoto, Timothy Middelkoop, and Daphne Siefert McCause. “RCD Nexus Day 2023 Final Report”. Zenodo, November 20, 2023.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10160680>

Staff Workforce Interest Group: This CaRCC interest group meets bi-monthly or more often and continues to set the foundation for gathering resource materials for RCD staff workforce development. The interest group has 83 members with diverse institutional representation.

This year the bi-monthly calls have included content and discussions relevant to the creation of RCD workforce resources that foster and reinforce RCD career development for those who support research and researchers. Content from the community calls included:

- Training plans for early career and onward as well as discussion and documentation of training plans, approaches, resources, and gaps in formal training.
- Topics and collaboration opportunities for PEARC24 submissions for papers, sessions, panels, workshops, and Birds of a Feather sessions.
- Review of the priorities developed during the RCD Nexus Day Staff Workforce Development workshop in July 2023.
- Multiple sessions on onboarding guidance for “First days,” “First weeks,” and “First months” as differentiated from training and staff development that became the foundation for a PEARC23 paper submission.
- Recap of Nexus Day 2023 and PEARC23, sharing summaries and insights from the workshop, as well as other sessions that all might not have been able to attend.
- RCD Mentoring Working Group-led discussion on the “Who, What, Where, When, and Why of a CaRCC Mentoring Program.”
- Discussion on the Job Family Framework and its overlay on career phases (content from a paper developed for PEARC22).
- Update from the CaRCC RCD Professionalization working group on their recharted objectives and planned activities.

Additional activities developed from the Staff and Student Workforce Development effort include:

- CaRCC Mentoring working group was formed and is working to develop a mentoring program for RCD professionals. Because career development for such a new field which is not supported by formal training, a specific degree or certified training, mentorship is critical to the growth and development of RCD professionals. Objectives for the program include partnering with successful mentoring programs, standard mentoring principles, and effective programmatic processes and procedures.
- Staff Workforce Development interest group standing committee on Gathering and Curating RCD Program Stories has developed an interview process and identified institutional representatives to tell the story of their RCD programs. These stories provide examples of programs, including their histories and successes. Interview write-ups will be published in the RCD Nexus portal, tagged for program characteristics, making them easily searchable until the portal has a full-features search capability.
- Presentations and small group breakout discussions have been recorded and one set of these documents was used to develop a PEARC23 short paper and presentation on the phases of an RCD career, discussing the complexity of an RCD career and the likely discrete phases, how one navigates into, out of, and within each phase. We expect this will be foundational to specific resources developed and provided through the RCD Nexus portal.
 - Timothy Middelkoop, Claire Mizumoto, Scotty Strachan, D Balamurugan, Scott Delinger, Jacob Fosso Tande, Deb McCaffrey, Ann Myatt James, David Reddy, and Patrick Schmitz. 2023. Career Phases in Research Computing and Data. In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '23), July 23-27, 2023, Portland, OR, USA. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 4 Pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3569951.3597562>
 - “2024-04-09: RCD Staff Workforce IG: Training plans discussion” <https://youtu.be/LHUDJs7Ghss>.

We continue to work closely with the Student Workforce Development workstream. Because we recognize the areas of overlap, we loosely alternate our monthly meeting time, and wherever it makes sense, we partner to move efforts forward.

5 Student Workforce Development

The focus of the Student RCD Workforce Development aspect of the project is to explore existing models for student RCD workforce development at both the undergraduate and graduate levels. During this reporting period, we have made progress on moving forward our main goal to create a guide and other resources that share leading practices and models from

organizations who are already doing this successfully. This team works in close coordination with the staff workforce development efforts.

The RCD Student workforce development interest group continues to grow and develop under co-chairs (Hillery, Haymore, Cheatham, and formerly Orendt) in conjunction with the RCD Staff workforce development Interest group chairs. The group currently has 78 members. The interest group meets at least bi-monthly, with some overlap with the Staff workforce development interest group.

This year the bi-monthly calls have included content and discussions relevant to the creation of RCD student workforce awareness and issues for pre-professionals, students enhancing their academic experience, and for the RCD institutional programs with a student workforce that enhance support to research and researchers. Content from the community calls included:

- Impact of Student RCD Workforce Experience student panel (October.)
- Student Program Models Funding Hiring Onboarding Discussion (February.)
- Student Program Models Funding Hiring Onboarding Discussion Part 2 (March.)

Onboarding has been a significant focus of a combined staff and student workforce development workshop as a continuing topic for discussion and in the creation of work products. One of the most interesting sessions was an RCD student workforce development interest group call that convened a panel of former RCD students who shared the impact of their experiences as a student employee in RCD. Overall, we have found benefit in the close collaboration with the Staff Workforce Development interest group and will continue to partner with them on community meetings and work products to be published in the RCD Nexus portal.

6 Job Family Matrix Adoption

Much of the energy this year went into work in Section 7.

The dissemination efforts for RCD Job Family Matrix were ongoing, with 66 downloads this year. This brings the total number of downloads to 366 with 299 unique email addresses across 174 different institutions. We have identified additional institutions that are willing to be interviewed in their implementation efforts. We will follow up with them in the upcoming year and publish the findings of the interviews.

7 RCD Workforce Survey

Much of this year's effort has focused on rebuilding the RCD Professionalization working group and updating its charter. Ashley Stauffer (Penn State University) and Kimberly Grasch (U of Chicago) have stepped up to co-chair the group. The aim of this working group is to create visualizations that provide deeper insight into the typical role and workflow of research facilitators. Membership has been updated and includes prior members Scott Yockel (Harvard) and Chris Reidy (Arizona), and new members Stefan Robila (Montclair), Ratika Giri (Northwestern), and Levi Dolan (Indiana). Since the role of a Facilitator has expanded and continues to be a focus of conversations at conferences, the group wanted to provide products that would represent the activities and relationships that are important for a Facilitator. The group reviewed a number of articles and explored a wide range of options for creating visualizations and mapping activities of facilitators with an interest in making them interactive. A number of new questions were proposed for a future survey. However, before embarking on a new survey, the group decided to perform a quick analysis of the 2021 survey data questions and focus on understanding the relationship between activities and roles and how they change through the lens from researcher-facing to systems-facing, software-facing, or data-facing. The previous survey data was extracted from the following questions:

- What is the highest degree you have earned?
- How many years of work experience do you have in total, including both RCD and non-RCD experience?
- How many years of work experience do you have as a Research Computing and Data (RCD) professional?
- Which of these best describes the field, content area, or domain of your formal education?
- For the portion of your position dedicated to RCD responsibilities, what percentage of your time is focused on each of the following areas (RCD facings)?
- Which activities do you spend at least 20% of your RCD time on? (Choose up to 5 activities that you spend the most time on.)

This resulted in a PEARC'24 short paper submission. Many of the key findings confirmed quantitatively what many of us have experienced anecdotally. Shown below is a representation of how the educational backgrounds flow into the various facings roles. It was interesting to see that a large chunk of life sciences professionals become facilitators, whereas computer and information or physical science professionals have a broad distribution of types of roles they play in research computing. When looking at the activities, one quickly realizes that the facing roles are not discrete and there is a continuum of activities between these roles.

Sankey plot representing respondent's field of education(left) mapped to majority facing role (center), subsequently mapped to top five work activities respondents spent at least 20% of their time on (right). Activities are defined as [project_management] project management; [security] security/compliance; [dev_service] developing new systems, services, or solutions; [financial] budget, finance, and/or securing human, financial, or capital resources; [tech_work] performing technical work (software development, data analysis, visualization, code optimization, data management, etc.) for specific researchers; [events] community development and event planning Administrative work; [tickets] customer service/ help desk/tickets; [reporting] metrics and reporting; [research] directly contributing to specific research projects intended for peer-reviewed publication Software development; [collab] partnering/ collaborating with others outside your primary work unit; [communication] communications/outreach to researchers/service users; [managing] managing or supervising others; [consulting] consulting with or advising researchers; [doc_teaching] documentation and/or teaching others; [systems] system operations/ administration; [other] other (write in responses)

In addition to looking at RCD activities mapped to a majority facing, we took a data-driven approach to reveal the activity pairs significantly correlated with each other (see below). This allows us to compare the survey results against our empirical understanding of the activities comprising each majority facing. This revealed strong positive correlations between some activities, resulting in the identification of five activity clusters as follows (Figure 3): (1) admin, financial (2) collab, project_management, managing, reports, events (3) communication, consulting, doc_teaching, tickets (4) research, tech_work, software (5) dev_service, systems, security, other. Of these, cluster (3) activities showed the strongest positive relationships amongst themselves. In these activities group 1 is indicative of research-facing, group 2 and 3 of

strategy/policy facing, group 4 of software-facing and data-facing, and group 5 for systems-facing.

Pairwise activity correlation matrix for activities on which respondents spent 20% time or more. Point size and color represent the strength and direction of correlation, respectively.

Surveying those in RCD roles, especially facilitators, on a regular cadence is required to collect data to (1) identify trends, (2) observe the profession and roles under varying lenses, and (3) represent the community and its impact. For this, we intend to produce and release a new survey to understand RCD roles better and expand our reach to include more R2 universities, minority-serving institutions, and historically black colleges/universities. The 2021 survey was considered preliminary and could not uncover all patterns. For example, nearly half of respondents to the 2021 survey selected no majority facing. As understanding and use of facings become commonplace amongst the community, we have the opportunity for better results leading to a deeper analysis. A future study will address gaps, such as the size of the facilitator’s team. It is expected that this data point could affect various aspects of the role, including work scope and career advancement prospects.

8 Program Administration

RCD Nexus consists of a set of related but distinct projects or workstreams, each managed by one of the Principal Investigators (PIs). The RCD Nexus team members also serve in various roles across CaRCC including the Logistics and Engagement Operations groups, the People Network Strategy and Policy-facing track, in addition to the roles in these workstreams as co-chairs of the RCD Capabilities Model, RCD Professionalization, RCD Career Arcs, and RCD Staff and Student workforce groups. This year we also started a Membership and Financial Models group and a Communications and Outreach group.

In order to keep all these work areas in sync and to enable identification of cross-project risks and opportunities, we conducted a series of program administration activities during the reporting period, including:

- Coordinated the June 2023 CaRCC Annual meeting with participation from RCD Nexus and CaRCC Advisory Committees, CaRCC chairs, People Network Coordinators, and several individuals from adjacent RCD Communities. The report is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8290478>
- Held the second annual RCD Nexus Day co-located with PEARC23. The report is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10160680>
- Lead and Contributed to CaRCC Chairs Monthly meetings
- Contributed to CaRCC Logistics Operations group (Brunson is co-chair, Schmitz, Cheatham, and McCanse are members).
- Contributed to CaRCC Engagement Operations Group (Mizumoto is co-chair, Cheatham and McCanse are members)
- Created and led the Membership and Financial Models group (McCanse is chair)
- Created the Communications and Outreach Interest Group (McCanse is co-chair)
- Managed project and engagement planning activities which reflect plans and progress against milestones
- Liaised with key collaborators and other community organization and project leads in order to establish and solidify partnerships (e.g., Brunson serves on external advisory boards for NSF ACCESS, NSF Jetstream2, NSF Chase-CI, Cloudbank, Nevada's NSF EPSCoR track 1 Harnessing the Data Revolution for Fire Science, etc)
- Managed sub-award contracts and oversaw spending
- Established program templates, policies, and procedures
- Posted presentations and other resources to the website and Zonodo for community use. (See section 10.)
- Disseminated program news and upcoming event information (see section 1)

9 Looking Forward

The work of RCD Nexus and CaRCC is driven and executed by a large cadre of volunteers (see Committees and Working groups below.) RCD Nexus support has provided critical infrastructure and central support for the growing CaRCC organization and serves to amplify the impact of these volunteers. However, the current level of support falls short of overall needs, hampering progress on important priorities. As the number of RCD professionals continues to grow, and we expand to support a larger and more diverse group of members, the need for coordination, facilitation, outreach, and communication has likewise grown within working groups, across the organization, and more broadly.

The growth and the reputation of CaRCC and RCD Nexus for delivering valuable tools, producing results, and building a strong community has led to an increase in requests for additional support in areas such as consulting, training, and communications, as well as demand for new resources such as gathering and curating leading practices in RCD, an RCD job board, and help with hiring. This growth has also led to an increased need for volunteer management resources and support to coordinate and enable the many volunteers who are eager to participate, as well as a greater need for outreach support to reach more communities and broaden representation within CaRCC.

Over the next year, we will continue progressing on the elements as described in the previous sections and continue developing the vision for CaRCC in support of the broad RCD Communities. In particular, via our supplemental funding and as described above, we will:

- Expand and sustain the Capabilities Model tools, create additional interactive graphics for the community data portal, and continue the work to provide useful tools to under-resourced institutions.
- Continue the development of the Career Arcs research and disseminate the research to the community.
- Host RCD Nexus Day in coordination with ACM PEARC24.
- Gather our core contributors and Advisory Committee members for a strategic retreat.

Additionally, our next phase priorities for CaRCC are:

- Refine and grow the CaRCC organization and enabling infrastructure to accelerate emerging RCD activities and increase their impact
- Expand our work in core areas of tools, leading practices, and curated training resources, and ensure these are highly visible and accessible

- Engage related programs (ACCESS, NAIRR Pilot, Virtual Residency, Campus Champions, US-RSE, EDUCAUSE RCG Community Group, CASC, CI leadership academy, CyberAmbassadors, etc.) to collaborate and expand their visibility, reach, and impact
- Build out the RCD Career Center to help job-seekers advance their careers and help hiring managers to build and grow their teams
- Provide expert consulting and training services
- Coordinate the development of a model for an RCD Professional Society
- Develop and recommend a financial and membership model for approval and adoption by CaRCC chairs

And our long term goals include:

- Ensure CaRCC has the necessary resources and services to fully support the expanding community activities that address the needs of RCD Professionals and advance research
- Accelerate the development of practical, high-visibility outcomes from CaRCC working groups
- Promote the continued growth of the CaRCC community and coordinate the establishment of a professional society
- Make concrete progress on key challenges in hiring, training, and advancing the careers of people in RCD professional roles
- Promote a clear understanding of RCD professional roles and their impact across the research community

10 Publications and Presentations

Publications

- Bayrd, Venice, Gwen Jacobs, Patrick Schmitz, Scotty Strachan, Patrick Clemins, and Frederick C. Jr. Harris. Minding the Gap: Leveraging Cyberinfrastructure to Transform Epscor Jurisdictions. Zenodo, June 29, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8097562>
- Cutcher-Gershenfeld, Joel, Torey Battelle, Dana Brunson, Thomas Cheatham, Jacob Fosso Tande, Douglas Jennewein, Julie Ma, Lauren A. Michael, Timothy Middelkoop, Henry Neeman, and Patrick Schmitz. 2023. Professionalization of Research Computing and Data: An Expanded Agenda. In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '23), July 23--27, 2023, Portland, OR, USA. ACM, New York, NY, USA 8 Pages. (Best Full Paper: Workforce Development). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3569951.3593610>
 PEARC23 Pulse Paper - Presentation - Published.pdf
- Hicks, John, and Forough Ghahramani. CaRCC Capabilities Model Focused Tools Engagement Guide and Script. Zenodo, April 11, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10960062>

- Maimone, Christina, Scott Yockel, Jay Alameda, Timothy Middelkoop, Amy Neeser, and Ashley Stauffer. CaRCC Research Computing and Data (RCD) Workforce Survey Data 2021 - Part 2. Zenodo, June 9, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8021611>
- Maimone, Christina, Carrie Brown, Kimberly Grasc, Chris Reidy, and Ashley Stauffer. Compensation of Academic Research Computing and Data Professionals. In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '23), July 23-27, 2023, Portland, OR, USA. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 12 pages 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3569951.3593599>
- McCause, Daphne. CaRCC 2023 Annual Retreat Report. Zenodo, August 28, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8290478>
- Middelkoop, Timothy, Claire Mizumoto, Scotty Strachan, D Balamurugan, Scott Delinger, Jacob Fosso Tande, Deb McCaffrey, Ann Myatt James, David Reddy, and Patrick Schmitz. 2023. Career Phases in Research Computing and Data. In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '23), July 23-27, 2023, Portland, OR, USA. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 4 Pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3569951.3597562>
 RCD Career Phases - PEARC23 Presentation - Published.pdf
- Mizumoto, Claire. "Research IT Tenets". Zenodo, March 1, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10732804>
- Schmitz, Patrick, Claire Mizumoto, Timothy Middelkoop, and Daphne Siefert McCause. RCD Nexus Day 2023 Final Report. Zenodo, November 20, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10160680>.
- Mizumoto, C. (2024). Research IT Tenets. Zenodo, March 1, 2024 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10732804>.
- Gladys Andino, Scott L. Delinger, Jacob Fosso Tande, Timothy Middelkoop, Claire Mizumoto, David P. Reddy, and Michael D. Weiner. "An Onboarding Checklist for Research Computing and Data Professionals," Zenodo, April 26, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11074226>

Presentations (listed chronologically)

- Claire Mizumoto, UCSD; Scotty Strachan, Nevada System of Higher Education; Forough Ghahramani, NJEdge; Timothy Middelkoop, Internet2; John Hicks, Internet2; Dana Brunson, Internet2 "The Campus Research Computing Consortium & RCD Nexus" Internet2 Community Exchange, Chicago IL, Thursday March 7, 2024.
 - <https://internet2.edu/commex24-abstracts/#thecampusresearchcomputingconsortium>
 - <http://internet2.edu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/20240307-CaRCC-RCD-Nexus-slides-12-CommEx.pdf>

- CaRCC Parade (January, virtual, CaRCC People Network)
<https://carcc.org/event/2024-carcc-parade/>,
<https://carcc.org/2023/12/20/2024-carcc-parade-bring-your-colleagues-to-carcc/>,
https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/117B_85nKRGca3WWO8eR65nNpV--fFRx4NVUdfpVIYeU/ (Attendance: 70), January 23, 2024.
- CaRCC Town Hall 2023
 Panel: Daphne McCanse, Dana Brunson, Tom Cheatham, Claire Mizumoto, Patrick Schmitz, Scott Yockel, Bob Freeman and Lauren Michael. Counts: RCD Capabilities Model Track 52 Student and Staff Workforce Track 55.
<https://internet2.edu/join-us-for-rcd-nexus-day-at-pearc23/>
<https://carcc.org/2023/05/02/join-us-for-rcd-nexus-day-at-pearc23/>
- Joel Cutcher-Gershenfeld, Torey Battelle, Dana Brunson, Thomas Cheatham, Jacob Fosso Tande, Douglas Jennewein, Julie Ma, Lauren A. Michael, Timothy Middelkoop, Henry Neeman, and Patrick Schmitz. 2023. Professionalization of Research Computing and Data: An Expanded Agenda. In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '23), July 23--27, 2023, Portland, OR, USA. ACM, New York, NY, USA 8 Pages. (Best Full Paper: Workforce Development). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3569951.3593610>
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- Timothy Middelkoop, Claire Mizumoto, Scotty Strachan, D Balamurugan, Scott Delinger, Jacob Fosso Tande, Deb McCaffrey, Ann Myatt James, David Reddy, and Patrick Schmitz. 2023. Career Phases in Research Computing and Data. In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '23), July 23-27, 2023, Portland, OR, USA. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 4 Pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3569951.3597562>
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- Christina Maimone, Carrie Brown, Kimberly Grasch, Chris Reidy, and Ashley Stauffer. Compensation of Academic Research Computing and Data Professionals. In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '23), July 23-27, 2023, Portland, OR, USA. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 12 pages 2023.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3569951.3593599>
- Dana Brunson, John Hicks, and Timothy Middelkoop. "Facilitating RCD Community Success". Presented at the 2023 Internet2 Technology Exchange (TechEX23), Minneapolis, Minnesota, September 19, 2023.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10027861>.
- Patrick Schmitz, "CaRCC and RCD Nexus: Supporting excellence in research computing and data (RCD)." Presented at the Mississippi HPC Conference, March 2024

- Patrick Schmitz, “How Do We Measure Up? A Capabilities Model and Community Dataset for Research Computing and Data.” Invited Keynote at the Spring Digital Research Infrastructure Connect Conference, June 1, 2023.
- Patrick Schmitz, “How Do We Measure Up? A Capabilities Model and Community Dataset for Research Computing and Data.” Presented to the Campus Champions, August 15, 2023.
- John Hicks, Presented Capabilities Model Focus Tools talk to SOX (Southern Regional), Virtual, August 24, 2023.
- John Hicks, Presented Capabilities Model Focus Tools talk to ILight (Indiana Regional), Virtual, August 17, 2023
- Quilt/NSF CC* PI meeting, Dana Brunson presented on the Communities of the Cyberinfrastructure Ecosystem, Sept. 27, 2023.
- Dana Brunson gave a presentation to Southwestern Oklahoma State University on Sept 19th about Community and Services available locally, regionally and nationally to the SWOSU community.
https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1BL7_LF9hi-bMCx5-ULodzxdzdiZL6FN-XJYDfDPad94/edit
- Dana Brunson, Lauren Michael, Timothy Middelkoop, Patrick Schmitz, and Forough Ghahramani, "Research IT Strategic Planning," at *Internet2 Community Exchange*, May 10th, Atlanta GA, 2023. Count 34
 - <https://internet2.edu/2023-internet2-community-exchange/program/abstracts/#researchit>
 - CX-23-Research IT Strategy.pptx
 - CX-23-Research IT Strategy.pdf
- Timothy Middelkoop, "Facilitating RCD Community Success," at the Great Plains Network (GPN) 2023 Annual Meeting, Kansas City, June 1st, 2023. Count 25.
 - <https://www.greatplains.net/gpnam2023/>
 - <https://gpn2023.sched.com/event/1Mp7k/breakout-2-c-facilitating-rcd-community-success>
 - 2023-06-01 Internet2 Research Engagement - GPN.pdf
- Patrick Schmitz, Keynote at “*Spring Digital Research Infrastructure Connect*”, June 1, 2023
 - <https://driconnect.alliancecan.ca/>
 - DRI Connect Keynote

Workshops

- CaRCC Annual Strategic retreat in June 2023, report available <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8290478>
- RCD Nexus Day co-located event (<https://rcd-nexus.org/rcd-nexus-day-2023/>) prior to PEARC23 with two workshops. RCD workforce development track and the RCD Capabilities Model track. Sunday, July 23rd, 2023

Events

- Internet2 hosted a “Coffee with CaRCC” for research computing and data professionals who are part of the Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC) on Wednesday November 15 from 10-11 a.m. at SC23. <https://internet2.edu/sc23-is-back-in-the-mile-high-city-internet2-will-meet-you-there/>
- Internet2 provided information about CaRCC, RCD Nexus, MS-CC and other community organizations along with literature and stickers at their sponsor booth at PEARC23. <https://internet2.edu/computing-for-the-common-good-at-pearc23/>

Media

- Community Exchange 2024 blog; <https://internet2.edu/countdown-to-2024-internet2-community-exchange-part2/>
- Internet2 Announcement: Timothy Middelkoop, ‘Computing for the Common Good’ at PEARC23: We’ll See You in Portland!, July 10 2023. <https://internet2.edu/computing-for-the-common-good-at-pearc23/>
- Internet2 Announcement: Daphne McCanse, “New Tool Now Available to Help Institutions Assess Their Research Computing and Data Programs,” November 2, 2023. <https://internet2.edu/new-tool-now-available-to-help-institutions-assess-their-research-computing-and-data-rcd-programs/>
- Internet2 Announcement: Daphne McCanse: “RCD Nexus supported the RCD Capabilities Assessment Tool release.” November 9, 2023 <https://internet2.edu/new-tool-now-available-to-help-institutions-assess-their-research-computing-and-data-rcd-programs/>
- Internet2 Announcement: Daphne McCanse, “Read the Report: Research Computing and Data (RCD) Nexus Day 2023,” November 29, 2023. <https://internet2.edu/research-computing-and-data-rcd-nexus-day-2023/>
- CaRCC Blog: Daphne McCanse, ‘RCD Nexus Day at PEARC23’, May 2, 2023. <https://carcc.org/2023/05/02/join-us-for-rcd-nexus-day-at-pearc23/>
- CaRCC Blog: Patrick Schmitz, “Where does RCD sit in the organization?,” September 14, 2023. <https://carcc.org/2023/09/14/where-does-rcd-sit-in-the-organization/>

- CaRCC Blog: Daphne McCause, “Seeking beta-testers for the new RCD Capabilities Model Tool”, October 16, 2023, <https://carcc.org/2023/10/16/help-beta-test-the-new-rcd-capabilities-model-tool/>
- CaRCC Blog: Daphne McCause, “New Capabilities Model Assessment Tool Now Available!,” November 2, 2023. <https://carcc.org/2023/11/02/new-rcd-capabilities-model-assessment-tool-now-available/>
- CaRCC Blog: Daphne McCause, “Read the report: RCD Nexus Day 2023” November 27, 2023. <https://carcc.org/2023/11/27/read-the-report-rcd-nexus-day-2023/>
- CaRCC Blog: Daphne McCause, “Capabilities Model Assessment Tool Upgraded to Version 2.1”, January 30, 2024, <https://carcc.org/2024/01/30/capabilities-model-assessment-tool-upgraded-to-version-2-1/>
- CaRCC Blog: Daphne McCause, “New! Engagement Facilitation Guide for Smaller and Emerging RCD Programs”, April 11, 2024, <https://carcc.org/2024/04/11/new-engagement-facilitation-guide-for-smaller-and-emerging-rcd-programs/>
- CaRCC Blog: Daphne McCause, “New Release: RCD Nexus Capabilities Model Visualization Portal”, April 09, 2024, <https://carcc.org/2024/04/09/new-release-rcd-nexus-capabilities-model-visualization-portal/>

People Network sessions - Recordings available on YouTube ([link](#)).

Plenaries:

- Community-Organized Call: REDCap Non-Health Data Discussion (11/6/2023)
- CaRCC Parade (1/23/2024)
- CaRCC Special Presentation The National AI Research Resource (NAIRR) with Katie Antypas (3/28/2024)

Data Facing Track (First Tuesdays):

- Accessibility Awareness Month- Kick-Off Community Discussion (5/2/2023)
- National Data Science Fabric (6/6/2023)
- Artificial Intelligence: The Beginning and the End of Human Wisdom (8/1/2023)
- Continuing Discussion on Artificial Intelligence (9/5/2023)
- ADSA Data ETHOS (10/3/2023)
- Overview of GIS (11/7/2023)
- Round Robin Track Discussion (1/2/2024)
- Common Workflow Language (2/6/2024)
- Future of the Data-Facing Track (3/5/2024)
- ICPSR: A Partner in Social Research (4/2/2024)

Emerging Centers Track (Third Wednesdays):

- CaRCC People Network Focus on Accessibility: Introduction to Web Accessibility (5/16/2023)
- The National Research Platform (NRP), presented by Larry Smarr, UCSD (6/21/2023)
- Centre for High Performance Computing, South Africa (8/16/2023)
- National Resources Series: CloudBank and Jetstream2 – Affordable Cloud Services (9/20/2023)
- Containers: How and Why (10/18/2023)
- Roundtable Discussion on Future Topics (1/17/2024)
- Communicating with your Users: Impacts, Services, and Documentation (2/21/2024)
- HPC in Africa (revisited) (3/20/2024)
- Open Science Grid (OSG) for Emerging Centers (5/15/2024)

Researcher-Facing Track (Second Thursdays):

- Current Research on Accessible Computing (5/11/2023)
- ACCESS Allocation Services: National cyberinfrastructure for research, development, and education (6/8/2023)
- Evolution of Containers for HPC (8/11/2023)
- Supporting Humanities Researchers: Roadblocks and Opportunities (9/14/2023)
- Amazon Lightsail for Research (10/12/2023)
- Exploring the Frontiers of CyberGIS and Geospatial Data Science (11/9/2023)
- What's Cool in 2024 (1/12/2024)
- JetStream2 – Researcher-Facing Resources and Support (2/8/2024)
- The Open Science Pool (OSPool) and OSG Services (3/14/2024)
- Generative Artificial Intelligence Tools: A Panel Discussion (4/11/2024)

Strategy and Policy-Facing Track (First Wednesdays):

- Documenting metrics for RCD programs (part 1) (6/7/2023)
- Documenting metrics for RCD programs (part 2) (7/5/2023)
- Reflections and discussion of PEARC23 (8/2/2023)
- RRIDs: Persistent Unique identifiers mark the things that are used in studies, key biological resources, and other important tools such as software tools, databases, core facilities, and now also instruments (9/6/2023)
- Satisfaction Surveys (10/4/2023)
- Meetings recap: Fall CASC Meeting, EDUCAUSE, + (11/1/2023)
- Major RCD expansion (Joint with EDUCAUSE RCD CG) (12/6/2023)
- Finance, Funding Partnerships (2/7/2024)
- Strategy and Policy challenges in supporting LLMs for research (3/6/2024)
- CASC and CNI recap (4/3/2024)

Systems-Facing Track (Third Thursdays):

- CaRCC Accessibility Month Discussion – Introduction to Universal Design (5/18/2023)

- Cluster Resource Management software and solutions - Part 1 (6/15/2023)
- Cluster Resource Management software and solutions – Part 2 (8/17/2023)
- CaRCC Systems Facing Roundup Session (9/21/2023)
- Containerizing HPC (10/19/2023)
- Navigating PBS to Slurm Migrations in Production Environments (1/18/2024)
- Overview of the Georgia Tech Rogues Gallery Testbed (2/15/2024)
- AI Support Community Discussion (3/21/2024)
- Supply Chain Challenges & Strategy Discussion (4/18/2024)

In our monthly call announcement, CaRCC provides information on additional community opportunities including the US Research Software Engineers and EDUCAUSE RCD Community Group monthly community calls, the OSG Consortium and NSF PATH weekly Office Hours, and the Regulated Research Community of Practice Community Discussions.

11 Committees and Working Groups

RCD Nexus Advisory Committee

Linda Akli, Southeastern Universities Research Association

Ewa Deelman, University of Southern California

Joel Cutcher-Gershenfeld, Brandeis University

Sandra Gesing, University of Illinois, Chicago

John Goodhue, Massachusetts Green High Performance Computing Center

Leah Lang, EDUCAUSE (withdrew due to change of position)

Jackie Milhans, Northwestern University

John Towns, University of Illinois

Von Welch, Indiana University (withdrew due to retirement)

CaRCC Advisory Committee

Jim Bottum (co-chair)

Jackie Milhans, Northwestern (co-chair)

Linda Akli, Texas Advanced Computing Center/University of Texas, Austin

Danielle Cooper, Ithaca S+R

Ana Hunsinger, Internet2

Ann Kovalchick, University of California, Merced

Erik Lundberg, University of Washington

Susan Mehringer, Cornell University

Henry Neeman, University of Oklahoma

Amy Neeser, University of California, Berkeley

Dan Stanzione, Texas Advanced Computing Center/University of Texas, Austin

Ashley Stauffer, Penn State University

CaRCC Chairs Leadership

Venice Bayrd, Montana State (EPSCoR Cyberinfrastructure)
Dana Brunson, Internet2 (RCD Capabilities Model; Logistics; RCD Nexus PI)
Thomas Cheatham, University of Utah (Decadal Survey; RCD Nexus co-PI; RCD Student Workforce Development)
Jason Christopher, University of California, Berkeley (HIPAA Challenges)
Sean Cleveland, The University of Hawaii System (EPSCoR Cyberinfrastructure)
Bob Freeman, Harvard Business School (People Network)
Kimberly Grasc, University of Chicago (RCD Professionalization)
Brian Haymore, University of Utah (RCD Student Workforce Development)
Betsy Hillery, Purdue University (RCD Student Workforce Development, Workforce Mentoring)
Gwen Jacobs, University of Hawaii (EPSCoR Cyberinfrastructure)
Alper Kinaci, Northwestern University (Workforce Mentoring)
Julie Ma, Massachusetts Green High Performance Computing Center (Engagement)
Deb McCaffrey, Arizona State University (HIPAA Challenges)
Lauren Michael, Internet2 (Logistics; People Network)
Timothy Middelkoop, Internet2 (RCD Staff Workforce Development)
Sam Porter, University of Maryland (Career Arcs)
Chris Reidy, University of Arizona (Engagement)
Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito Consulting (RCD Capabilities Model; Career Arcs; RCD Nexus co-PI)
Scotty Strachan, Nevada System of Higher Education (EPSCoR Cyberinfrastructure)
Ashley Stauffer, Penn State University (RCD Professionalization)
Michael Weiner, Georgia Institute of Technology (RCD Staff Workforce Development)
Scott Yockel, Harvard University (RCD Nexus co-PI)

Capabilities Model Working Group

Group website: <https://carcc.org/rcdcm/>
Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito (co-chair)
Dana Brunson, Internet2 (co-chair)
Thomas Cheatham, University of Utah
James Deaton, Internet2
Don DuRousseau, University of Arkansas
Paul Fischer, University of Utah
Forough Ghahramani, NJEdge
John Hicks, Internet2
Lauren Michael, Lauren Michael Consulting, LLC
Scotty Strachan, Nevada

Focused Tools Committee:

Group website: <https://carcc.org/rcdcm/>

John Hicks, Internet2 (co-chair)

Forough Ghahramani, NJEdge (co-chair)

Sarvani Chadalapaka, University of California, Merced

Paul Arias, Rutgers University

Kirk Anne, Rochester Institute of Technology

Izzat Alsmadi, Texas A&M University

Mike Austin, University of Vermont

Dana Brunson, Internet2

James Deaton, Internet2

Bala Desinghu, Rutgers University

Don DuRousseau, University of Arkansas

Chuntida Harinnitisuk, University of Texas Health, San Antonio

Robert Henschel, Indiana University

Lauren Michael, Lauren Michael Consulting, LLC

Stefan Robila, Montclair State University

Widodo Samyono, Jarvis Christian University

Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito Consulting

Andy Sherman, Yale University

Scotty Strachan, University of Nevada Reno

Rick Tuthill, University of Massachusetts

Shu Wan, University of Buffalo

RCD Professionalization Working Group

Group website: <https://carcc.org/rcd-professionalization/>

Kimberly Grasch, University of Chicago (co-chair)

Ashley Stauffer, Penn State University (co-chair)

Lauren Michael, Internet2

Deb McCaffrey, Arizona State University

Christina Maimone, Northwestern

Chris Reidy, University of Arizona

Stefan Robilas, Montclair State

Levi Dolan, Indiana University

Scott Yockel, Harvard University

RCD Career Arcs Working Group

Group Website: <https://carcc.org/career-arcs/>

Sam Porter, University of Maryland (co-chair)
Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito Consulting (co-chair)
Gladys Andino, University Virginia
Sarvani Chadalapaka, University of California, Merced
Shafaq Chaudhry, University of Central Florida
Betsy Hillery, Purdue University
Kerk Kee, Texas Tech University
Arman Pazouki, Purdue University
Preston Smith, Purdue University

EPSCoR CI Council Interest Group

Group website: <https://carcc.org/epscor-ci/>

This group emerged from the previous EPSCoR CI Working group which produced a report [“Minding the Gap: Leveraging Cyberinfrastructure to Transform EPSCoR Jurisdictions”](#)

Chairs:

Venice Bayrd, Montana State (co-Chair)
Sean Cleveland, University of Hawai'i System (co-Chair)
Scotty Strachan, Nevada System of Higher Education (co-Chair)

Steering Committee (in addition to the co-chairs):

Dana Brunson, Internet2
Fred Harris, University of Nevada, Reno
Gwen Jacobs, University of Hawaii
Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito Consulting

CI Council members:

Venice Bayrd, University of Montana
Patrick Clemins, University of Vermont
Sean Cleveland, University of Hawaii
Vincent Dela Cruz, University of Guam
Sarah Diesburg, University of Iowa
Anthony Elam, University of Kentucky
Liam Forbes, University of Alaska
Kelly Harrigan, University of Virgin Islands
Jeffrey Hamerlinck, University of Wyoming
Henry Neeman, University of Oklahoma
Michael Navicky, University of Mississippi
Ashley Podhradsky, Dakota State University
Scotty Strachan, Nevada System of Higher Education
Isis Serna, University of New Mexico
Luke Sheneman, University of Idaho

Brent Van Aartsen, Dakota State University
Kevin Wentworth, University of Maine

RCD Staff Workforce Development Interest Group

Group website: <https://carcc.org/staff-and-student-workforce-development/>

Timothy Middelkoop, Internet2 (co-chair)

Claire Mizumoto, University of California San Diego (co-chair)

Michael Weiner, Georgia Institute of Technology (incoming co-chair)

Gladys Andino, University of Virginia

Janae Baker, Rutgers University

Joshua Baller, University of Minnesota

Caughlin Bohn, University of Nebraska

Dana Brunson, Internet2

Katia Bulekova, Boston University

Tom Cheatham, University of Utah

Michael Colee, UC Santa Barbara

Scott Delinger, Altadel Computing

Jonathan Dursi, Research Computing Teams

Tony Elam, University of Kentucky

Nathan Elger, University of Southern California

Grace Faustino, University of New Mexico

Mego Franks, Wake Forest School of Medicine

Layla Freeborn, University of Colorado-Boulder

Bob Freeman, Harvard Business School

Jeff Gardner, University of British Columbia

Jill Gemmill, Clemson University

Forough Ghahramani, NJEdge

Toolika Ghose, University of Nebraska

Toolika Ghose, University of Nebraska System

Tom Gulbransen, National Science Foundation

Scott Hampton, University of Notre Dame

Chuntida Harinnitisuk, University of Texas Health Science Center at San Antonio

Brian Haymore, University of Utah

Betsy Hillery, Purdue University

Susan Ivey, North Carolina State University

Matthew Keeler, University of Missouri System

Kathryn Kelley, Coalition for the Academic Scientific Computation (CASC)

Alper Kinaci, Northwestern University

Matt Lacy, Texas A&M University

AJ Lauer, National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR)
Shuai Liu, University of Arkansas
Erik Lundberg, University of Washington
Jose Martinez, University of California, Los Angeles
Deb McCaffrey, Arizona State University
Daphne McCause, CaRCC
Randy Melen, Stanford University
Benjamin Meyers, Rochester Institute of Technology
Jackie Milhans, Northwestern University
Julia Mullen, Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Mary Murphy, University of Wisconsin-Madison
Pradeep Nagaraj, Bath University
Henry Neeman, University of Oklahoma-Norman
Amy Neeser, University of California, Berkeley
Alastair Neil, George Mason University
Janna Nugent, Northwestern University
Amy Nurnberger, Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Colin Odden, The Ohio State University
Anita Orendt, University of Utah
Arman Pazouki, Purdue University
Dylan Perkins, University of Colorado, Boulder
Joe Rasche, Texas A&M/University San Antonio
Mike Renfro, Tennessee Technological University
Nick Rochlin, University of British Columbia
Jayshree Sarma, George Mason University
Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito Consulting
Sandy Shew, The Ohio State University
Swabir Silayi, George Mason University
Christopher Simmons, Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Winona Snapp-Childs, Indiana University
Ashley Stauffer, Penn State University
Sheri Stebenne, Texas A&M University
Michael Stoppay, Montclair State University
Scotty Strachan, Nevada System of Higher Education, NevadaNet
Georgia Stuart, University of Massachusetts, Amherst
Berhane Temelso, George Mason University
Mandy Terrill, Oregon Health & Science University
Laura Theademan, Purdue University
Kimberly Thomas, University of California, San Diego

Nur Goldner Cohen Tzedek, University of California, Berkeley
Ravi Vadapalli, University of Miami
Qinghua Wang, University of Delaware
Amanda Warren-Glowe, Purdue University
Feng Zhang, Stonybrook University
Biru Zhou, McGill University

RCD Student Workforce Development Interest Group

Group website: <https://carcc.org/staff-and-student-workforce-development/>

Thomas Cheatham, University of Utah (co-chair)
Betsy Hillery, Purdue University (co-chair)
Anita Orendt, University of Utah (outgoing co-chair)
Brian Haymore, University of Utah (incoming co-chair)
Gladys Andino, University of Virginia
Janae Baker, Rutgers University
Venice Bayrd, Montana State University
Rebecca Belshe, Arizona State University
Dana Brunson, Internet2
Katia Bulekova, Boston University
Dhruva Chakravorty, Texas A&M University
Dhruv Chakravorty, Texas A&M University
Michael Colee, University of California, Santa Barbara
Scott Coughlin, Northwestern University
Virginia Do, National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR)
Matthew Dorsey, North Carolina State University
Jonathan Dursi, Research Computing Teams
Nathan Elger, University of Southern California
Jacob Fosso Tande, NC State University (formerly UNC Greensboro)
Nikki Galloway, Old Dominion University
Jill Gemmill, Clemson University
Forough Ghahramani, NJEdge
Tom Gulbrandsen, National Science Foundation
Amanda Hassenplug, Purdue University
Brian Haymore, University of Utah
Kathryn Kelley, Coalition for Academic Scientific Computation (CASC)
Alper Kinaci, Northwestern University
Elizabeth Kinney, University of British Columbia
Matt Lacy, Texas A&M University
AJ Lauer, National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR)

Shuai Liu, University of Arkansas
Erik Lundberg, University of Washington
Jose Martinez, University of California, Los Angeles
Deb McCaffrey, Arizona State University
Daphne McCause, CaRCC
Benjamin Meyers, Rochester Institute of Technology
Timothy Middelkoop, Internet2
Claire Mizumoto, University of California, San Diego
Mary Murphy, University of Wisconsin-Madison
Pradeep Nagaraj, Bath University
Ryan Nakashima, San Diego Supercomputer Center/University of California, San Diego
Henry Neeman, University of Oklahoma, Norman
Amy Neeser, University of California, Berkeley
Jenny Nguyen, San Diego Supercomputer Center/University of California, San Diego
Amy Numberger, Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Daria Orłowska, Western Michigan University
Marinus Pennings, Texas A&M University
Dylan Perkins, University of Colorado, Boulder
Craig Pohl, Washington University in St Louis
David Reddy, University of South Carolina
Chris Reidy, University of Arizona
Mike Renfro, Tennessee Technological University
Carolina Roe-Raymond, Princeton University
Rahul Salla, Arizona State University
Paula Sanematsu, FAS Research Computing, Harvard University
Jayshree Sarma, George Mason University
Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito Consulting
Andrew Sherman, Yale University
Swabir Silayi, George Mason University
Karsten Siller, University of Virginia
Sheri Stebenne, Texas A&M University
Michael Stoppay, Montclair State University
Scotty Strachan, Nevada System of Higher Education, NevadaNet
Georgia Stuart, University of Massachusetts, Amherst
Berhane Temelso, George Mason University
Laura Theademan, Purdue University
Chuck Thompson, Yale University
Nur Goldner Cohen Tzedek, University of California, Berkeley
Ravi Vadapalli, University of Miami

Shu Wan, University of Buffalo
Amanda Warren-Glowe, Purdue University
Michael Weiner, Georgia Tech University
Biru Zhou, McGill University

Decadal Survey Interest Group

Website: <https://carcc.org/working-groups/decadal-survey/>

Thomas Cheatham (co-chair)
Ruth Marinshaw (co-chair)
Kirk Anne, Rochester Institute of Technology
Tim Boerner, University of Illinois
Sharon Broude Geva, Independent consultant
Dana Brunson, Internet2
Dhruva Chakravorty Texas A&M University
Vessela Ensberg, University of California, Davis
Deb McCaffrey, Arizona State University
Kaylea Nelson, Yale University
Jen Schopf, Texas Advanced Computing Center
Andy Sherman, Yale University
Dan Stanzione, Texas Advanced Computing Center
Scotty Strachan, Nevada System of Higher Education
John Towns, National Center for Atmospheric Research
Mike Warfe, Case Western Reserve
Jason Wells, Harvard University

HIPAA Challenges Interest Group

Website: <https://carcc.org/hipaa-challenges/>

Deb McCaffrey, Arizona State University (co-chair)
Jason Christopher, University of California, Berkeley (co-chair)
Ian Brooks, University of Colorado, Anschutz
Jil Gemmill, Clemson University
Jim Kenyon, University of Michigan
Tobin Magle, Northwestern University
Andrea McColl, University of California, Los Angeles
Timothy Stark, University of Colorado, Anschutz
Mike Warfe, Case Western University

People Network

Website: <https://carcc.org/people-network/>

Bob Freeman, Harvard Business School (co-chair)

Lauren Michael, Internet2 (co-chair)

Researcher-Facing Track (<https://carcc.org/people-network/researcher-facing-track/>)

Justin Booth, Michigan State University (co-coordinator)

Tobin Magle, Northwestern University (co-coordinator)

Steering Committee:

Gladys Karina Andino Bautista, University of Virginia

Carrie Brown, Penn State University

Katia Bulekova, Boston University

Martin Cuma, University of Utah

Annelie Rugg, UCLA

Kurt Showmaker, Jackson Laboratories

Systems-Facing Track (<https://carcc.org/people-network/systems-facing-track/>)

Brian Haymore, University of Utah (co-coordinator)

Betsy Hillary, Purdue University (co-coordinator, departing)

Matthew Smith, Columbia University (co-coordinator)

Steering Committee:

John Blaas, National Center for Atmospheric Research

Jim Leous, Penn State University

Sai Pinnepalli, Louisiana State University

Dori Sajdak, University of Buffalo

Jason Wells, Harvard University

Data-Facing Track (<https://carcc.org/people-network/data-facing-track/>)

Amy Koshoffer, University of Cincinnati (co-coordinator)

Deb McCaffrey, Arizona State University (co-coordinator)

Steering Committee:

Sean Cleveland, University of Hawaii

Venice Bayrd, University of Montana

Strategy & Policy-Facing Track

(<https://carcc.org/people-network/strategy-and-policy-facing-track/>)

Amit Amritkar, Penn State, (co-coordinator)

Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito (co-coordinator)

Steering Committee:

Melissa Cragin, Rice University

Vessela Ensberg, University of California, Davis

Susan Ivey, North Carolina State University

Rich Knepper, Cornell University

Jackie Milhans, Northwestern University

Preston Smith, Purdue University

Jim Wilgenbusch, University of Minnesota

Emerging Centers Track (<https://carcc.org/people-network/emerging-centers-track/>)

Rich Knepper, Cornell University (co-coordinator)

Patrick Clemens, University of Vermont (co-coordinator)

Jane Combs, University of Cincinnati (co-coordinator, departing)

Steering Committee:

Kirk Anne, Rochester Institute of Technology

Alex Feltus, Clemson University

Susan Ivey, North Carolina State University

Preston Smith, Purdue University

Jason Wells, Harvard University

Logistics Operations Group

Dana Brunson, Internet2 (co-chair)

Lauren Michael (co-chair)

Thomas Cheatham, University of Utah

Bob Freeman, Harvard Business School

Timothy Middelkoop, Internet2

Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito Consulting

Daphne McCause, CaRCC

Metrics Committee

Bob Freeman, Harvard Business School (chair)

Kirk Anne, Rochester Institute of Technology

Sean Cleveland, University of Hawaii System

Kerk Kee, University of Texas, Austin

Anita Orendt, University of Utah

Chris Reidy, University of Arizona

Gil Speyer, Arizona State University

Gabriel Smith, Cornell University

Wei Yin, Columbia University

Web Committee

Abby Blackett, University of Utah

Daphne McCause, CaRCC

Sean Cleveland, University of Hawaii System

Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito Consulting

Anita Orendt, University of Utah

Engagement Operations Group

Julie Ma, Massachusetts Green High Performance Computing Center (co-chair)

Chris Reidy, University of Arizona (co-chair)

Cyd Burrows-Schilling, University of California San Diego

Tom Cheatham, University of Utah

Bob Freeman, Harvard Business School

Brian Haymore, University of Utah

Ann Kovalchick, University of California Merced, retired

Claire Mizumoto, University of California San Diego

Tracy Smith, University of Illinois at Urbana Champaign

Recently formed groups:

Membership and Financial Models Group

Daphne McCanse, CaRCC (co-chair)

Ashley Stauffer, Penn State (co-chair)

Jack Bradley, Idaho State University

Dana Brunson, Internet2

Bob Freeman, Harvard University

Kathryn Kelley, Coalition for Academic Scientific Computation (CASC)

Deb McCaffrey, Arizona State University

Lauren Michael, Lauren Michael Consulting, LLC

Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito Consulting

Mentorship working group

Betsy Hillary, Purdue University (co-chair)

Alper Kinaci, Northwestern University (co-chair)

Kathryn Kelley, Coalition for Academic Scientific Computation (CASC)

Claire Mizumoto, University of California, San Diego

Anita Orendt, University of Utah

Communications and Outreach Interest Group

Daphne McCanse, CaRCC (co-chair)

Eric Adams, Purdue University (co-chair)

Research Cybersecurity Interest Group

Bobby Edemala, Cornell University (co-chair)

Jeffrey Weekley, UC Santa Cruz (co-chair)